

**MEDITERRANEANS: NORTH AFRICA AND EUROPE IN
AN AGE OF MIGRATION, C. 1800-1900**
by Julia A. Clancy-Smith

Berkeley: University of California Press, 2011
(xix + 445 pages, bibliography, index, illustrations, maps) \$49.95 (cloth)

Reviewed by Omar Cheta

While the history of the Ottoman Empire and its Arab provinces is the subject of countless academic studies in English, there is a dearth of scholarship on North Africa. For this reason alone, Julia Clancy-Smith's study on trans-Mediterranean migration in the modern period is a valuable contribution. *Mediterraneans* also invites us to rethink the contemporary politics of (im)migration in Europe and North Africa in light of its nineteenth-century precursors. In addition, it reexamines the impact of pre-colonial social configurations on colonial and post-colonial polities.

Unlike post-World War II migratory trends, the overwhelming majority of trans-Mediterranean migration during the nineteenth century flowed south. Accordingly, the book traces migrants from Europe, the Mediterranean islands, and French Algeria into Tunis and its environs. It relies primarily on British and French consular records and private papers. The study focuses on the period between the French colonization of Algeria in 1830 and Tunisia in 1881, although the treatment of some topics, such as Catholic female missionaries and seaside residences, deals

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with later decades. As the author notes in her introduction, “the first six chapters tend to fall into the genre of prosopography,” since they construct the collective experience of migrants through the critical reading of numerous historical anecdotes (17). The last three chapters explore the trajectory of a specific group, place, or individual.

The book’s introduction lays out conceptual and methodological issues. Most importantly, it emphasizes the instability of the boundary between Europe and the Ottoman North African coast. Instead of identifying a fixed boundary, *Mediterraneans* describes a borderland region, which it terms the “central Mediterranean corridor” through which migrants were ceaselessly moving: “The corridor’s contours ran roughly from Tunis to the Algiers region, Marseilles, and Leghorn, then to Sicily, Malta, and back along the Tunisian coastline” (11). Thus, Tunis, one of the main nodes of this corridor, emerges as an ideal site for the study of trans-Mediterranean migration.

Next, the book draws a sketch of Tunis, paying particular attention to its institutional make-up, spatial organization, and the composition of its populace. Of particular interest is how residents of the city differentiated between long-standing European residents, or cultural creoles, and more recent migrant communities, and how each of these groups perceived and interacted with their newly arrived compatriots. Chapter two takes a step back from Tunis in order to explore the multiple factors that led would-be migrants to leave their homelands, as well as the reasons why Tunis was a likely destination. Furthermore, it draws attention to the intermediaries who made the movements of large numbers of migrants possible in the first place. For example, fishermen who conventionally roamed the seas between Sardinia or Sicily and Tunis in search of a better harvest (or who transported smuggled goods) increasingly used their small boats to ferry migrants to the southern shores of the Mediterranean. In addition, “freelance recruitment agents sprang up across Italy to entice laborers to North Africa” (81).

The following three chapters, collectively entitled “Making a Living,” follow migrants around Tunis recounting the employment opportunities available to them and explaining how their particular social positioning influenced their career prospects. Banned from engaging in wage labor in their homeland, Maltese women were more likely to opt for the type of

work they were most familiar with, namely, domestic labor in Tunisian households. Maltese men, on the other hand, sought to utilize the strong affinities between their native tongue and both Arabic and Italian, and those displaying sufficient linguistic competence were able to find work in the governor's court. Work-related qualifications aside, competition—among migrants and between them and local job seekers—was significant. The competition between subsistence migrants and newly manumitted slaves, especially for domestic service, is a case in point. Although employment statistics are unavailable, ship lists suggest that by the 1830s, middle-class European migrants were no longer exclusively dependent on their extended (or imagined) kin in Tunis to find jobs. This tendency points to the gap between middle-class migrants' perceptions of their new destination as a land of opportunities and the social realities they were likely to face once they arrived there and struggled to earn a living.

The most innovative chapter in this trilogy, "The Sea, Contraband, and Other Illicit Activities," examines sea-related activities that the Tunisian state prohibited "as special economic niches within a single but structurally diverse economic system" (161). This definition integrates transactions in prohibited commodities, such as gunpowder and hashish, into the history of the mainstream economy. Moreover, the focus on "illicit" economic activities brings to light the convergence of several historical trends and allows us to capture them at play. The high demand for hashish, for example, correlated with the expansion of coffee houses, thus linking this commodity to public sociability. A concurrent development that fueled both hashish consumption and coffee house expansion was the inflow of migrants from French Algeria, be they dislocated Algerians or deserting colonial soldiers. Moreover, because the hashish trade involved many European subjects who enjoyed extraterritorial privileges, the legal prosecution of such activities was often extremely difficult. In this way, the study of a prohibited commodity illuminates the interplay of sociability, migration, colonialism, and law.

Chapter six documents the manifestations of legal pluralism on the ground. It touches upon topics such as the legal status of consular buildings and the introduction of passports. More interestingly, it shows how "consular justice varied according to age, social class, nationality, and, above all, gender" (229). Europeans' religious conversion to Islam is par-

ticularly revealing in this respect because it was located at the intersection of local and foreign jurisdictions. A less common scenario but one that tested the limits of existing judicial arrangements was a convert's decision to revert to his or her former religion. In such cases, Tunisia's governor and interested consuls cooperated to formulate extralegal solutions. In order to relieve the convert of severe legal punishment, in this case death, they sent him or her to another country.

The last three chapters cover more specific historical case studies but delve deeper into each of them. The first narrates the history of the first Catholic female missionary group to operate in Tunisia, the Sisters of Saint-Joseph de l'Apparition. It views the Sisters as a migrant group and argues that they were allied with Tunisia's governors through concentrating their efforts on containing poor European immigrants rather than proselytizing. The following chapter takes us into Tunisia's Mediterranean villages to show how beach houses, particularly their harems, were key sites for forging alliances between local and foreign elites. The final chapter retells the story of Tunisia's ambitious governor Khayr al-Din (r. 1873–1877) as a migrant who arrived in the Ottoman Empire as a slave and navigated the Empire's patron circles in Istanbul and Tunis. This account differs markedly from the common accounts of Khayr al-Din's life, which mostly focus on his career as a statesman.

Despite its limited geographic focus, *Mediterraneans* contributes to broader academic subjects, especially borders, colonialism, and gender. Its understanding of borders as constantly shifting spaces is particularly illuminating in light of the profusion of voices striving to define what Europe is through shutting out its peripheries, particularly North Africa and Turkey. By recording the experiences of ordinary Europeans in nineteenth-century Tunisia, the book emphasizes the commonplaceness of migration in human history and, therefore, constitutes a critique of the contemporary politics of xenophobia. As for colonialism, the book argues convincingly that it was not synonymous with superior forms of government, nor was it necessarily the bearer of modernity. To the contrary, pre-colonial arrangements were often more inclusive and not as tension-ridden. For example, before 1881, the Sisters of Saint-Joseph were assimilated into Tunisian society through restraining their proselytizing tendencies and undertaking social services, including girls' education.

The French colonial administration, on the other hand, supported proselytizing Muslims and created schools that it made increasingly difficult for non-French subjects to attend. Finally, instead of dealing with women as a separate subject, the book treats them as full historical actors through integrating them into its main narrative line. Accordingly, female prostitution is discussed as one instance of a larger range of illicit activities, while harems, often considered exotic places, emerge “as sites of diplomacy, gift giving, and information gathering” (290).

Mediterraneans is bound to become essential reading for students of the modern Middle East. The book’s length and level of detail might render it unpractical to assign in its entirety except in classes dedicated primarily to Tunisian history. However, its thematic organization and the lucidity and coherence of each chapter allow for selective reading.